

Application of Significant Structure Concept to the Mixture Dielectric Constant of Some Polar-Polar Binary Systems

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The values of mixture dielectric constant were calculated for different compositions of a few polar-polar homogeneous binary liquid systems by the application of the significant structure concept of Eyring and coworkers. It was shown that the concept predicted mixture dielectric constant, composition for maximum deviation from ideality and the excess dielectric constant quite satisfactorily for the systems considered by using only pure component data.

JOHN and Eyring¹ calculated the dielectric constants of water-methanol and water-dioxane mixtures using the domain theory of dielectric constants of hydrogen bonded liquids and the concepts of Significant Structure Theory (SST). They showed that the agreement of the calculated and experimental values was quite satisfactory. Recently, the present authors followed a different method of determining certain SST parameters and calculated the mixture viscosities of a few apolar-apolar and apolar-polar binary liquid mixtures². In view of the simplicity of determining one of the major SST parameters namely the volume of solid-like molecules in a liquid by author's method, it was considered worthwhile to calculate the dielectric constants of some polar-polar binary liquid mixtures by adopting the technique and test its applicability in such cases.

Results and Discussion

Applying the concept of significant liquid structure theory to polar-polar binary liquid mixtures, the mixture dielectric constant ϵ_m can be given by the following equation^{3(a)}.

$$\frac{3\epsilon_m(\epsilon_m - n_m^2)}{(2\epsilon_m + n_m^2)} = \frac{4\pi N}{V_m} \left[\epsilon_m (n_m^2 + 2) \right]^2$$

$$\left[\frac{V_m}{V} \left(X_1^2 \frac{\mu_1^2 G_1}{kT} + X_2^2 \frac{\mu_2^2 G_2}{kT} + 2X_1 X_2 \frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{kT} (G_1 G_2)^{1/2} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{V_m}{V} \right) \left(X_1 \frac{\mu_1^2}{3kT} + X_2 \frac{\mu_2^2}{3kT} \right) \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

where V is the molar volume at the temperature of investigation, V_s is the molar volume just before melting, n is the refractive index appropriate to electronic and atomic polarizabilities, μ is the dipole moment, G is an adjustable parameter, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature,

N is the Avogadro's number, X is the mole fraction and the subscripts $m, 1$ and 2 stand for mixture, component 1 and component 2, respectively.

Evaluation of the parameters V_m, V_{sm}, n_m, G_1 and G_2 :

Remembering that V_{sm} does not widely differ from V_m and occurs in the ratio form in equation (1) as is evident from its slight rearrangement, we can write

$$\frac{V_{sm}}{V_m} = \frac{X_1 V_{s1} + X_2 V_{s2} + V^E}{X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2 + V^E} \quad \dots (2)$$

Since the excess quantities V_s^E and V^E are very small in comparison to V_s and V of the pure components, equation (2) can be approximated to

$$\frac{V_{sm}}{V_m} \sim \frac{X_1 V_{s1} + X_2 V_{s2}}{X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2} \quad \dots (3)$$

As required by equation (3) the values of V_s for pure components were obtained by the method of Singh and Sinha² whereas the values of V for pure components were taken from literature.

In order to evaluate n_m , the appropriate combining rule gives

$$n_m = X_1^2 n_1 + X_2^2 n_2 + 2X_1 X_2 (n_1 n_2)^{1/2} \quad \dots (4)$$

It may be pointed out here that the values of n_1 and n_2 to be used in equation (4) should be the values extrapolated to infinite wavelength. However, the contribution of such extrapolated values in comparison to the corresponding values for sodium-D line is rather insignificant and as such the latter values were used. As regards the determination of G_1 and G_2 , the same were calculated from equation (1) reduced to pure component form by putting $X_2 = 0$, removing the subscripts 2 and m and using the pure component values of ϵ, n, V, V_s and μ .

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Thus, the experimental values of V , n_D , ϵ , μ and the computed values of V_s and G for pure components (Table 1) alongwith mixture parameters V_m ,

TABLE 1—STANDARD AND CALCULATED VALUES OF DIFFERENT PARAMETERS

Parameters	Temp. °C	CH ₃ OH	C ₂ H ₅ OH	CH ₃ COCH ₃	H ₂ O
V_s cc		33.45	48.10	59.25	17.85*
σ A[4b]		3.626	4.530	4.600	2.641
μ Debye[4a]		1.70	1.66*	2.69*	1.84
V cc	15	40.299	58.058	72.94	18.033
	20	40.556	58.364	73.43	18.049
	25	40.815	58.678	73.97	18.070
ϵ [5a]	15	34.2	26.40	21.85	82.00
	20	33.7	25.70	21.40	80.00
	25	32.8	24.90	20.90	78.00
n_D [6 a-c]	15	1.3305	1.36345	1.36140	1.33347
	20	1.3284	1.36143	1.35868	1.33296*
	25	1.3265*	1.35941	1.35596	1.33250
G	15	1.171	1.306	0.472	0.959
	20	1.186	1.303	0.477	0.954
	25	1.195	1.298	0.479	0.949

*Ref [7b] *Ref [7c] *Ref [7d] *Ref [7a] *Ref [3b]

V_{sm} and n_m as obtained from equations (2) to (4) were used to calculate the values of ϵ_m by equation (1) for different compositions of the polar-polar binaries, H₂O(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) at 20°, C₂H₅OH(1)+CH₃COCH₃(2) at 25°, CH₃OH(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) at 15° and H₂O(1)+CH₃COCH₃(2) at 20°.

While comparing the calculated and experimental mixture dielectric constant data, it was observed that very often the values of $(\epsilon_m)_{expt}$ for $X_1=0$ and/or $X_1=1$ did not exactly tally with the standard dielectric constant values for the pure components used to calculate G values from equation (1) as reduced to pure component form. In order to account for such variations, $(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$, which represents the adjusted value of the calculated mixture dielectric constant $(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$ from equation (1) was obtained by the following equation.

$$(\epsilon'_m)_{cal} = (\epsilon_m)_{cal} + X_1(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon'_1) + X_2(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon'_2) + \Delta^E \quad \dots (5)$$

where ϵ'_1 and ϵ'_2 are equal to $(\epsilon_m)_{expt}$ for $X=1$ and $X=0$, respectively while ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the standard dielectric constant values for the pure components 1 and 2 used in equation (1) as reduced to pure component form. The excess quantity Δ^E , which represents the deviation from ideality in difference quantity $[(\epsilon'_m)_{cal} - (\epsilon_m)_{cal}]$, is considered negligible in comparison to $(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$ and neglected while evaluating $(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$. The values of $(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$ and $(\epsilon_m)_{expt}$ for various compositions of the binaries considered are given in Tables 2A to 2D.

Further, defining excess dielectric constant ϵ^E by $\epsilon^E = \epsilon_m - [X_1 \epsilon_{1expt} + X_2 \epsilon_{2expt}] \quad \dots (6)$

the values of $(\epsilon^E)_{expt}$ and $(\epsilon^E)_{cal}$ were obtained from corresponding $(\epsilon_m)_{expt}$ and $(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$, respectively and plotted against X_1 . One such typical plot is given in Fig. 1. The values of $(X_{1,max})_{expt}$, $(X_{1,max})_{cal}$,

TABLE 2A—MIXTURE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT FOR SYSTEM H₂O(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) AT 20°

Mole fraction X ₁	ϵ_{mexpt} [5b]	ϵ^E_{expt}	$(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (1)	$(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (5)	%* Deviation	$(\epsilon^E)_{cal}$
0.0	26.50	0.00	25.76	26.50	-0.00	-0.00
0.1	27.80	-4.23	27.38	28.23	-1.54	-3.80
0.2	29.40	-8.16	29.27	30.24	-2.84	-7.32
0.3	31.60	-11.49	31.52	32.73	-3.59	-10.36
0.4	34.40	-14.22	34.23	35.42	-2.96	-13.20
0.5	37.80	-16.25	37.56	38.86	-2.80	-15.29
0.6	42.30	-17.38	41.74	43.16	-2.02	-16.52
0.7	48.00	-17.21	47.14	48.67	-1.39	-16.54
0.8	55.90	-14.84	54.38	56.02	-0.22	-14.72
0.9	66.20	-10.07	64.57	66.33	-0.19	-9.94
1.0	81.80	0.00	79.93	81.80	0.00	0.00

* % Deviation = $\left[\frac{(\epsilon_m)_{expt} - (\epsilon'_m)_{cal}}{(\epsilon_m)_{expt}} \right] \times 100$

TABLE 2B—MIXTURE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT FOR SYSTEM C₂H₅OH(1)+CH₃COCH₃(2) AT 25°

Mole fraction X ₁	ϵ_{mexpt} [8a]	ϵ^E_{expt}	$(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (1)	$(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (5)	%* Deviation	$(\epsilon^E)_{cal}$
0.0	20.87	0.00	20.93	20.87	0.00	0.00
0.1	20.79	-0.46	21.24	21.16	-1.75	-0.09
0.2	20.73	-0.90	21.56	21.46	-3.51	-0.18
0.3	20.82	-1.20	21.91	21.78	-4.61	-0.23
0.4	20.90	-1.50	22.27	22.12	-5.85	-0.28
0.5	21.15	-1.63	22.65	22.49	-6.31	-0.29
0.6	21.59	-1.57	23.06	22.87	-5.93	-0.29
0.7	22.18	-1.36	23.49	23.28	-4.96	-0.26
0.8	22.84	-1.09	23.95	23.72	-3.84	-0.21
0.9	23.68	-0.63	24.44	24.19	-2.14	-0.12
1.0	24.69	0.00	24.97	24.69	0.00	0.00

TABLE 2C—MIXTURE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT FOR SYSTEM CH₃OH(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) AT 15°

Mole fraction X ₁	ϵ_{mexpt} [8b]	ϵ^E_{expt}	$(\epsilon_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (1)	$(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$ from eqn. (5)	%* Deviation	$(\epsilon^E)_{cal}$
0.0	25.02	0.00	26.55	25.02	0.00	0.00
0.1	25.10	-0.82	27.09	25.69	-2.35	-0.23
0.2	25.34	-1.49	27.66	26.40	-4.18	-0.43
0.3	25.71	-2.08	28.28	27.15	-5.61	-0.63
0.4	26.20	-2.43	28.94	27.95	-6.67	-0.68
0.5	26.78	-2.76	29.65	28.80	-7.53	-0.74
0.6	27.59	-2.35	30.42	29.71	-7.66	-0.73
0.7	28.54	-2.30	31.26	30.68	-7.41	-0.67
0.8	30.11	-2.13	32.16	31.72	-5.33	-0.53
0.9	31.91	-1.24	33.15	32.84	-2.90	-0.31
1.0	34.05	0.00	34.22	34.05	0.00	0.00

$(\epsilon^E_{max})_{expt}$ and $(\epsilon^E_{max})_{cal}$ as determined graphically from the curves similar to those in Fig. 1 are given in Table 3.

A close scrutiny of Tables 2A to 2D reveals that the values of $(\epsilon'_m)_{cal}$ agree quite satisfactorily with the corresponding values of $(\epsilon_m)_{expt}$ in each case. The % deviations for the binaries H₂O(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) at 20°, C₂H₅OH(1)+CH₃COCH₃(2) at 25°, CH₃OH(1)+C₂H₅OH(2) at 15° and H₂O(1)+CH₃-

TABLE 2D—MIXTURE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT FOR SYSTEM H₂O(1) + CH₃COCH₃(2) AT 20°

Mole fraction X ₁	ε _m expt [5b]	ε _m ^R expt	(ε _m) _{cal} from eqn. (1)	(ε _m) _{cal} from eqn. (5)	%* Deviation	(ε _m) _{cal}
0.0	20.70	- 0.00	21.48	20.70	0.00	0.00
0.1	22.40	- 4.41	22.75	22.28	+ 0.52	- 4.53
0.2	24.50	- 8.42	24.40	24.19	+ 1.26	- 8.73
0.3	27.00	- 12.03	26.32	26.37	+ 2.33	- 12.66
0.4	30.00	- 15.14	28.69	29.00	+ 3.32	- 16.14
0.5	34.50	- 16.75	31.59	32.16	+ 6.79	- 19.09
0.6	39.60	- 17.76	35.48	36.31	+ 8.30	- 21.05
0.7	46.10	- 17.37	40.76	41.85	+ 9.22	- 21.62
0.8	54.60	- 14.98	48.29	49.64	+ 9.07	- 19.94
0.9	66.50	- 9.19	59.90	61.51	+ 7.50	- 14.18
1.0	81.80	0.00	79.93	81.80	0.00	0.00

minima in mixtures rich in component 1 in each case. As regards the values of (ε_{max}^E)_{cal}, they show the same sign as that of (ε_{max}^E)_{expt} even though the deviation in their magnitude, in some cases, is rather large.

In view of the existence of specific short range molecular interactions as evidenced by the highly associating nature and polarity of the components of binaries selected, it is quite satisfying that the significant liquid structure concept leads to a suitable procedure for the computation of mixture dielectric constant and binary composition for maximum nonideality within permissible deviation

TABLE 3—THE EXPERIMENTAL AS WELL AS CALCULATED VALUES OF (X₁ max) AND (ε_{max}^R) FOR DIFFERENT BINARY SYSTEMS

System	Temp °C	(X ₁ max) _{expt}	(X ₁ max) _{cal}	(ε _{max} ^R) _{expt}	(ε _{max} ^R) _{cal}
H ₂ O(1) + C ₂ H ₅ OH(2)	20	0.65	0.65	- 17.29	- 16.70
C ₂ H ₅ OH(1) + CH ₃ COCH ₃ (2)	25	0.52	0.52	- 1.64	- 0.30
CH ₃ OH(1) + C ₂ H ₅ OH(2)	15	0.60	0.55	- 2.85	- 0.75
H ₂ O(1) + CH ₃ COCH ₃ (2)	20	0.62	0.67	- 17.90	- 21.80

Fig. 1. Variation of ε^R vs X₁ for H₂O(1) + C₂H₅OH(2) binaries at 20°.

COCH₃(2) at 20° are less than -4, -7, -8 and -10%, respectively.

Table 3 shows that the values of (X₁ max)_{cal} compare well with those of (X₁ max)_{expt} for the binaries H₂O(1) + C₂H₅OH(2) at 20° and C₂H₅OH(1) + CH₃COCH₃(2) at 20° while for the rest two, they deviate within ±10% but predict correctly the existence of

limits by using only pure component data and predicts correctly the existence of minima in the composition range which compares well with that obtained on the basis of experimental data.

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